

Glutathione Peroxidase (GSH-PX) Assay Kit

(Colorimetric Method)

Serial No: A005

Pack: 50T/24S
100T/48S

Nanjing Jiancheng Bioengineering Institute

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1. INTRODUCTION

This kit can be used for laboratory research only.

(1) Assay significance:

Glutathione peroxidase (GSH-PX) is a widespread, important hydrogen peroxidase in organisms. It catalyzes reduced glutathione's reduction reaction with peroxide diagnostically leads to protection of cell structure and functions. GSH-PX's active site is Se-cysteine, selenium is necessary part of GSH-PX, 1 mol GSH-PX contains 4g selenium. GSH-PX activity can be used as a biochemical indicator of Se level in vivo.

(2) Assay principle:

Glutathione peroxidase (GSH-PX) can catalyze peroxide (H₂O₂) and reduced glutathione (GSH) to produce H₂O and oxidized glutathione (GSSG). GSH-PX activity can be represented by its enzymatic reaction rate. It is able to calculate enzyme activity by measuring GSH consumption in this enzymatic reaction.

GSH-PX activity is represented by catalyzed GSH reaction rate. These two substrates can undertake redox reaction without enzyme (non-enzymatic reaction), so GSH consumption caused by non-enzymatic reaction must be deducted when you calculate enzyme activity in conclusion.

GSH content assay: GSH reacts with dithio-dinitrobenzoic acid to produce 5-thio-dinitrobenzoic acid anions with relatively stable yellow color. It is able to calculate GSH content by measuring absorbance at 412nm.

2. REAGENT COMPOSITION & PREPARATION

The whole kit can be stored at 4°C for 6 months.

(1) Reagent composition & preparation of 100T/48S kit:

Reagent No.	Name	Quantity and storage condition
Reagent 1	Stock solution	2ml × 1 bottle, can be stored at 4°C for 6 months
<p>Reagent 1 working solution preparation: When use, take 0.1ml stock solution, add distilled water until mixture volume reaches 10ml (equals to 100 times dilution). Please use working solution soon after preparation, how much you use, how much you make. Can be stored at 4°C.</p>		
Reagent 2	Powder A	1 bottle, can be stored at 4°C for 6 months
	<p>Solution A preparation: Add 170ml 90~100°C hot distilled water, dissolve sufficiently.</p>	
	Solution B	50ml × 1 bottle, can be stored at 4°C for 6 months
<p>Reagent 2 working solution preparation: Mix prepared Solution A and Solution B sufficiently. This mixture is supersaturated solution, so if there are crystals seed out after cooling and placing, then take supernatant for experiment. Can be stored at 4°C or room temperature for 6 months.</p>		
Reagent 3	Powder	1 bottle, can be stored at 4 for 6 months
<p>Reagent 3 working solution preparation: Add 200ml distilled water to dissolve, can be stored in plastic bottle (gift from our Institute) for 6 months.</p>		

Reagent 4	Powder	1 bottle, can be stored at 4°C away from light for 6 months
<p>Reagent 4 working solution preparation: Add 50ml distilled water to dissolve, can be stored at 4°C away from light for 6 months.</p>		
Reagent 5	Powder	4 vials, can be stored at 4°C away from light for 6 months
<p>Reagent 5 working solution preparation: Add 10ml distilled water each vial to dissolve, can be stored at 4°C away from light for 5 days.</p>		
Reagent 6	GSH standard powder	3.07mg × 4 vials, can be stored at 4°C away from light for 6 months
Reagent 7	GSH standard solvent stock solution	10ml × 1 bottle, can be stored at 4°C away from light for 6 months
<p>Standard solvent working solution preparation: Mix stock solution with double distilled water at ratio of 1:9 (equals to 10 times dilution) to make working solution. Please use working solution soon after preparation. Can be stored at 4°C.</p>		
<p>1mmol/LGSH solution preparation: GSH 's molecular weight is 307. Before assay, add 1 vial (3.07mg) GSH standard powder to GSH standard solvent, add solvent until mixture volume reaches 10ml, this solution is considered as 1mmol/L GSH solution. Please use working solution soon after preparation.</p>		
<p>100 μ mol/LGSH solution preparation: Mix 2ml 1 mmol/LGSH solution and 18ml GSH solution working solution, adjust volume to 20ml. This solution is used to draw standard curve. If you don't want to draw standard curve, then you can skip this step. (See in Appendix V: GSH standard curve preparation).</p>		

20 μ mol/L GSH standard solution: Take 0.2ml 1mmol/L GSH solution, add GSH standard solvent working solution until mixture volume reaches to 10ml. This solution is considered as 20 μ mol/L GSH standard solution.

(2) Reagent composition & preparation of 50T/24S kit:

Reagent No.	Name	Quantity and storage condition
Reagent 1	Stock solution	1ml \times 1 bottles, can be stored at 4 $^{\circ}$ C for 6 months
<p>Reagent 1 working solution preparation: When use, take 0.1ml stock solution, add distilled water until mixture volume reaches 10ml (equals to 100 times dilution). Please use working solution soon after preparation, how much you use, how much you make. Can be stored at 4$^{\circ}$C.</p>		
Reagent 2	Powder A	1 bottle, can be stored at 4 $^{\circ}$ C for 6 months
	<p>Solution A preparation: Add 85ml 90~100$^{\circ}$C hot distilled water, dissolve sufficiently.</p>	
	Solution B	25ml \times 1 bottle, can be stored at 4 $^{\circ}$ C for 6 months
<p>Reagent 2 working solution preparation: Mix prepared Solution A and Solution B sufficiently. This mixture is supersaturated solution, so if there are crystals seed out after cooling and placing, then take supernatant for experiment. Can be stored at 4$^{\circ}$C or room temperature for 6 months.</p>		
Reagent 3	Powder	1 bottle, can be stored at 4 $^{\circ}$ C for 6 months
<p>Reagent 3 working solution preparation: Add 100ml distilled water to dissolve, can be stored in plastic bottle (gift from our Institute) for 6 months.</p>		

Reagent 4	Solution	25ml \times 1 bottle, can be stored at 4 $^{\circ}$ C away from light for 6 months
Reagent 5	Powder	2 vials, can be stored at 4 $^{\circ}$ C away from light for 6 months
<p>Reagent 5 working solution preparation: Add 10ml distilled water each vial to dissolve, can be stored at 4$^{\circ}$C away from light for 5 days.</p>		
Reagent 6	GSH standard powder	3.07mg \times 2 vials, can be stored at 4 $^{\circ}$ C away from light for 6 months
Reagent 7	GSH standard solvent stock solution	5ml \times 1 bottle, can be stored at 4 $^{\circ}$ C away from light for 6 months
<p>Standard solvent working solution preparation: Mix stock solution with double distilled water at ratio of 1:9 (equals to 10 times dilution) to make working solution. Please use working solution soon after preparation. Can be stored at 4$^{\circ}$C.</p>		
<p>1mmol/LGSH solution preparation: GSH 's molecular weight is 307. Before assay, add 1 vial (3.07mg) GSH standard powder to GSH standard solvent, add solvent until mixture volume reaches 10ml, this solution is considered as 1mmol/L GSH solution. Please use working solution soon after preparation.</p>		
<p>100 μ mol/LGSH solution preparation: Mix 2ml 1mmol/LGSH solution and 18ml GSH solution working solution, adjust volume to 20ml. This solution is used to draw standard curve. If you don't want to draw standard curve, then you can skip this step. (See in Appendix V: GSH standard curve preparation).</p>		
<p>20μmol/L GSH standard solution: Take 0.2ml 1mmol/L GSH solution, add GSH standard solvent working solution until mixture volume reaches to 10ml. This solution is considered as 20μmol/L GSH standard solution.</p>		

3. REQUIRED EQUIPMENTS & REAGENTS

- A spectrophotometer capable of measuring absorbance at 412nm
- Thermostatic water bath or air bath capable of controlling temperature at 37 °C
- Centrifuge (different procedures need different kinds of centrifuge)
- Micropipets and tips
- Vortex mixer
- A source of pure water (preferably double distilled water and double distilled water)
- Physiological saline and homogenate medium

4. WHOLE BLOOD GSH-PX ACTIVITY ASSAY

(1) Sample pretreatment:

Hemolysate preparation:

- ① Take 20 μ l heparin anticoagulated whole blood, dilute with distilled water to 1ml, 1:49 hemolysate is made. Dilute 10 μ l mouse/rat blood with distilled water to 1ml, 1:99 hemolysate is made.
- ② Mix sufficiently, place for 5 minutes until hemolysate in glass tube appears **completely transparent towards light**, then you can start assay.
- ③ GSH-PX activity in prepared hemolysate can maintain for only 45~60 minutes (extend to 120 minutes in cold weather. If you have not enough time to assay in the same day, then you can keep you samples in anticoagulated whole blood fridge(4°C~8°C), enzyme activity keeps stable in 2~3 days.

Note 1: Please do preliminary experiment before formal experiment, details in **example of hemolysate optimal sampling concentration and optimal sampling volume probing**.

Note 2: Please make sure that erythrocytes are completely haemolyzed before measure blood GSH-PX activity (completely haemolyzed blood appears **transparent** towards light, **if it is not transparent enough, then you can freeze-thaw it once**. But erythrocytes of some rats and pigs can not be placed below 0°C or they will be hard to haemolyze. For example, erythrocytes of diabetic rats and some normal rats are very hard to haemolyze after freezing. It is better to take 1-2 samples to do pretesting before formal experiment.

(2) Operation procedures:

① Enzymatic reaction:

Reagent	Nonenzyme tube	Enzyme tube
1mmol/L GSH (ml)	0.2	0.2
Hemolysate to assay (ml)		0.2
Pre-warm in 37°C water bath for 5 minutes		
Reagent 1 (37°C pre-warm) (ml)	0.1	0.1
React in 37°C water bath for 5 minutes accurately		
Reagent 2 (ml)	2	2
Hemolysate to assay (ml)	0.2	
Mix sufficiently, centrifugate at 3500~4000rpm for 10 minutes. Take 1ml supernatant to do chromogenic reaction.		

② Chromogenic reaction:

Reagent	Blank tube	Standard tube	Nonenzyme tube	Enzyme tube
GSH standard solvent working solution (ml)	1			
20 μ mol/L GSH standard solution (ml)		1		
Supernatant (ml)			1	1
Reagent 3 working solution (ml)	1	1	1	1
Reagent 4 working solution (ml)	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25
Reagent 5 working solution (ml)	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05
Mix sufficiently, place at room temperature for 15 minutes, transfer in cuvettes of 1cm light path, measure OD values of all tubes at 412nm (adjust zero by distilled water)				

(3) Calculation:

Definition: Reacts at 37°C for 5 minutes, 1 μ mol/L GSH concentration decreasing (already deduct effect of nonenzymatic reaction) in reaction system per 4 μ l whole blood is considered as 1 enzyme activity unit (U).

Formula:

$$\text{Whole blood GSH-PX activity} = \frac{\text{OD}_{\text{Nonenzyme}} - \text{OD}_{\text{Enzyme}}}{\text{OD}_{\text{Standard}} - \text{OD}_{\text{Blank}}} \times \text{Standard solution concentration (20}\mu\text{mol/L)} \times \text{Dilution times (5}^* \times \frac{1+X^{**}}{1+49^{***}})$$

Note: * According to operation table of enzymatic reaction, 0.5ml reaction solution is mixed with 2ml Reagent 2, this fact equals to 5 times dilution, so multiply with 5.

** X is whole blood dilution times. For example, if you dilute at ratio of 1:99, then X=99.

*** 1+49: When hemolysate is diluted at ratio of 1:49, taking 0.2ml hemolysate to assay equals to taking 4 μ l whole blood.

(4) Example of hemolysate optimal sampling concentration and optimal sampling volume probing :

① **Sample source:** Fresh normal rat tail whole blood

② **Sample pretreatment:**

Dilute rat whole blood with distilled water at ratio of 1:24, 1:49, 1:59, 1:69, 1:79, 1:89, 1:99, 1:149, 1:199 separately in order to make a series of hemolysates of different concentrations. Take 0.2ml a series of hemolysates of different concentrations to assay according to whole blood assay operation table.

③ Results:

OD _{Blank}		0.041	
OD _{Standard}		0.163	
Sampling concentration	OD _{Enzyme}	OD _{Nonenzyme}	Inhibition ratio
1 : 24	0.079	0.451	82.48%
1 : 49	0.096	0.452	78.76%
1 : 59	0.107	0.450	76.22%
1 : 69	0.118	0.452	73.89%
1 : 79	0.130	0.450	71.11%
1 : 89	0.144	0.450	68.00%
1 : 99	0.163	0.449	63.70%
1 : 149	0.231	0.450	48.67%
1 : 199	0.298	0.449	33.63%

④ Conclusion:

According to data above, optimal sampling concentration of 1:149 can make inhibition ratio (inhibition ratio= $(OD_{Contrast}-OD_{Sample})/OD_{Contrast} \times 100\%$) in the range of 45%~55%. As result, it is better to take 0.2ml 1:149 diluted normal rat tail whole blood for GSH-PX formal experiment.

(5) Calculation examples:

Example 1: Take 0.2ml 1:49 diluted hemolysate to assay. In results, OD_{Nonenzyme} is 0.463, OD_{Enzyme} is 0.228, OD_{Standard} is 0.165, OD_{Blank} is 0.041. Calculate as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Whole blood GSH-PX activity} &= \frac{OD_{\text{Nonenzyme}} - OD_{\text{Enzyme}}}{OD_{\text{Standard}} - OD_{\text{Blank}}} \times \text{Standard solution concentration} \times 5 \times \frac{1+49}{1+49} \\ &= \frac{0.463-0.228}{0.165-0.041} \times 20 \times 5 \times \frac{50}{50} = 189.52 \text{ U} \end{aligned}$$

Example 2: Take 0.2ml 1:149 diluted rat hemolysate to assay, length of water bath is 5 minutes. In results, OD_{Nonenzyme} is 0.451, OD_{Enzyme} is 0.205, OD_{Standard} is 0.165, OD_{Blank} is 0.041. Calculate as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Whole blood GSH-PX activity} &= \frac{OD_{\text{Nonenzyme}} - OD_{\text{Enzyme}}}{OD_{\text{Standard}} - OD_{\text{Blank}}} \times \text{Standard solution concentration} \times 5 \times \frac{1+149}{1+49} \\ &= \frac{0.451-0.205}{0.165-0.041} \times 20 \times 5 \times \frac{150}{50} = 595.16 \text{ U} \end{aligned}$$

5. GSH-PX ACTIVITY ASSAY IN TISSUE, MITOCHONDRION & CELL MEMBRANE

(1) Sample pretreatment:**① 10% tissue homogenate preparation:**

a. Take tissue piece (0.2~1g), wash by ice-cold physiological saline. Remove blood, dry by filter paper, transfer in 5~10ml small flask.

b. Use cylinder to measure volume of precooling **homogenate medium**(PH7.4, 0.01mol/L sucrose, 0.01mol/L Tris-HCl, 0.0001mol/L EDTA2Na solution) or **physiological saline**. Volume of homogenate medium or 0.86% physiological saline should be 9 times as tissue weight, transfer 2/3 total volume of homogenate medium or physiological saline into small flask. Cut tissue to small pieces by ophthalmology small scissor as quick as possible (please put small flask in ice water bath in hot weather).

c. Pour small tissue pieces to glass homogenate tube, then wash tissue residual by 1/3 volume of homogenate medium or 0.86% physiological saline, transfer all mixture into glass homogenate tube then start to make homogenate. Use left hand to hold homogenate tube to make sure its bottom in icewater bath, use right hand to insert bar in tube, grind by up-down rolling for several dozens times (6~8 minutes), grind sufficient to make sure tissue becomes homogenate. You can also use tissue triturator to grind at 10000~15000r/min to make 10% homogenate; incision tissue homogenizer can also be used (homogenate length: 10 seconds/time, interval is 30 seconds, do 3~4 times at 0~4°C) . Cardiac muscle needs longer homogenate time.

Note: Take optimal concentration to assay (according to pretesting result).

d. Centrifugate prepared 10% homogenate at 3000rpm (by common centrifuge or low temperature centrifuge) for 10~15 minutes. Remove sediment, keep supernatant.

e. Take supernatant for various kinds of assay according to your require.

② Mitochondrion preparation:

Take 5~10ml 10% tissue homogenate, centrifugate at 1000~2000rpm for 10 minutes (by common centrifuge or low temperature low speed centrifuge). Take supernatant, centrifugate at 8000~10000rpm (by low temperature high speed centrifuge) for 15 minutes, sediment is mitochondrions.

(2) Operation procedures:

① Enzymatic reaction:

Reagent	Nonenzyme tube	Enzyme tube
1mmol/L GSH (ml)	0.2	0.2
Hemolysate to assay (ml)		0.2
Pre-warm in 37°C water bath for 5 minutes		
Reagent 1 (37°C pre-warm) (ml)	0.1	0.1
React in 37°C water bath for 5 minutes accurately		
Reagent 2 (ml)	2	2
Hemolysate to assay (ml)	0.2	
Mix sufficiently, centrifugate at 3500~4000rpm for 10 minutes. Take 1ml supernatant to do chromogenic reaction.		

② Chromogenic reaction:

Reagent	Blank tube	Standard tube	Nonenzyme tube	Enzyme tube
GSH standard solvent working solution (ml)	1			
20 μ mol/L GSH standard solution (ml)		1		
Supernatant (ml)			1	1
Reagent 3 working solution (ml)	1	1	1	1
Reagent 4 working solution (ml)	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25
Reagent 5 working solution (ml)	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05
Mix sufficiently, place at room temperature for 15 minutes, transfer in cuvettes of 1cm light path, measure OD values of all tubes at 412nm (adjust zero by distilled water)				

(3) Calculation:

Definition: 1 μ mol/L GSH concentration decreasing (already deduct effect of nonenzymatic reaction) in reaction system per mg protein per minute is considered as 1 enzyme activity unit (U).

Note: Tissue protein assay: According to experimental methodology, use biuret method, Coomassie brilliant blue method, ultraviolet method or salicylsulfonic acid method to measure tissue protein content in milligrams.

Formula:

$$\text{Tissue GSH-PX activity} = \frac{\text{OD}_{\text{Nonenzyme}} - \text{OD}_{\text{Enzyme}}}{\text{OD}_{\text{Standard}} - \text{OD}_{\text{Blank}}} \times \frac{\text{Standard solution concentration (20}\mu\text{mol/L)}}{\text{Dilution times (5*)}} \div \frac{\text{Reaction time length}}{\text{(Sampling volume} \times \text{Protein content in sample)}}$$

Note: * According to operation table of enzymatic reaction, 0.5ml reaction solution is mixed with 2ml Reagent 2, this fact equals to 5 times dilution, so multiply with 5.

(4) Example of tissue homogenate optimal sampling concentration and optimal sampling volume probing:

① **Sample source:** Use normal mouse liver tissue to make 10% liver homogenat supernatant, dilute with physiological saline to 1% for assay.

② **Sample pretreatment:**

Dilute 1% liver homogenate with physiological saline to 1.0%, 0.5%, 0.4%, 0.3%, 0.25%, 0.1%, 0.05% separately in order to make a series of homogenates of different concentrations. Take 0.2ml a series of homogenates of different concentrations to assay according to tissue assay operation table.

③ Results:

OD _{Blank}		0.041	
OD _{Standard}		0.163	
Sampling concentration	OD _{Enzyme}	OD _{Nonenzyme}	Inhibition ratio
0.05%	0.411	0.463	11.23%
0.1%	0.356	0.464	23.28%
0.2%	0.283	0.462	38.74%
0.25%	0.244	0.461	47.07%
0.3%	0.213	0.462	53.89%
0.4%	0.175	0.461	62.04%
0.5%	0.145	0.460	68.47%
1.0%	0.085	0.460	81.52%

④ Conclusion:

According to data above, optimal sampling concentration of 0.25% can make inhibition ratio (inhibition ratio = $((OD_{Contrast} - OD_{Sample}) / OD_{Contrast}) \times 100\%$) in the range of 45%~55%. As result, it is better to take 0.2ml 0.25% normal mouse liver tissue homogenate for GSH-PX formal assay.

(5) Calculation examples:

Example 1: Take 0.2ml 0.25% mouse liver tissue homogenate to assay. In results, OD_{Nonenzyme} is 0.480, OD_{Enzyme} is 0.172, OD_{Standard} is 0.163, OD_{Blank} is 0.041, protein content in 1% homogenate is 0.910mg/ml, standard solution concentration is 20 μ mol/L. Calculate as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Liver tissue GSH-PX activity} &= \frac{OD_{\text{Nonenzyme}} - OD_{\text{Enzyme}}}{OD_{\text{Standard}} - OD_{\text{Blank}}} \times \text{Standard solution concentration (20}\mu\text{mol/L)} \times \text{Dilution times} \\ &\quad \div \frac{\text{Reaction time length}}{(\text{Sampling volume} \times \text{Protein content in sample})} \\ &= \frac{0.480 - 0.172}{0.163 - 0.041} \times 20 \times 5 \div 5 \div (0.910 \div 4 \times 0.2) \\ &= 1109.71 \text{ U} \end{aligned}$$

Note: * 0.25% mouse liver homogenate is used to measure GSH-PX activity, 1% mouse liver homogenate is used to measure protein content, so in calculation, it should be divided by 4.

Example 2: Take 0.2ml 0.5% crucian liver tissue homogenate to assay. In results, OD_{Nonenzyme} is 0.454, OD_{Enzyme} is 0.264, OD_{Standard} is 0.163, OD_{Blank} is 0.041, protein content in 1% homogenate is 0.8367mg/ml, standard solution concentration is 20 μ mol/L. Calculate as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Liver tissue GSH-PX activity} &= \frac{OD_{\text{Nonenzyme}} - OD_{\text{Enzyme}}}{OD_{\text{Standard}} - OD_{\text{Blank}}} \times \text{Standard solution concentration (20}\mu\text{mol/L)} \times \text{Dilution times} \\ &\quad \div \frac{\text{Reaction time length}}{(\text{Sampling volume} \times \text{Protein content in sample})} \\ &= \frac{0.454 - 0.264}{0.163 - 0.041} \times 20 \times 5 \div 5 \div (0.8367 \div 2 \times 0.2) \\ &= 372.266 \text{ U} \end{aligned}$$

Note: * 0.5% crucian liver homogenate is used to measure GSH-PX activity, 1% crucian liver homogenate is used to measure protein content, so in calculation, it should be divided by 2.

Example 3: Take 0.2ml 10% rat testis tissue homogenate to assay. In results, OD_{Nonenzyme} is 0.468, OD_{Enzyme} is 0.258, OD_{Standard} is 0.163, OD_{Blank} is 0.041, protein content in 10% homogenate is 6.941mg/ml, standard solution concentration is 20 μ mol/L . Calculate as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Testis tissue GSH-PX activity} &= \frac{\text{OD}_{\text{Nonenzyme}} - \text{OD}_{\text{Enzyme}}}{\text{OD}_{\text{Standard}} - \text{OD}_{\text{Blank}}} \times \frac{\text{Standard solution concentration}}{(20\mu\text{mol/L})} \times \text{Dilution times} \\ &\quad \div \frac{\text{Reaction time}}{\text{length}} \div (\text{Sampling volume} \times \text{Protein content in sample}) \\ &= \frac{0.468 - 0.258}{0.163 - 0.041} \times 20 \times 5 \div 5 \div (6.941 \times 0.2) \\ &= 24.799 \text{ U} \end{aligned}$$

6. GSH-PX ACTIVITY ASSAY IN BLOOD SERUM (OR PLASMA)

(1) Operation procedures:

① Enzymatic reaction:

Reagent	Nonenzyme tube	Enzyme tube
1mmol/L GSH (ml)	0.2	0.2
Hemolysate to assay (ml)		0.1
Pre-warm in 37 $^{\circ}$ C water bath for 5 minutes		
Reagent 1 (37 $^{\circ}$ C pre-warm) (ml)	0.1	0.1
React in 37 $^{\circ}$ C water bath for 5 minutes accurately		
Reagent 2 (ml)	2	2
Hemolysate to assay (ml)	0.1	
Mix sufficiently, centrifugate at 3500~4000rpm for 10 minutes. Take 1ml supernatant to do chromogenic reaction.		

② Chromogenic reaction:

Reagent	Blank tube	Standard tube	Nonenzyme tube	Enzyme tube
GSH standard solvent working solution (ml)	1			
20μmol/L GSH standard solution (ml)		1		
Supernatant (ml)			1	1
Reagent 3 working solution (ml)	1	1	1	1
Reagent 4 working solution (ml)	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25
Reagent 5 working solution (ml)	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05
Mix sufficiently, place at room temperature for 15 minutes, transfer in cuvettes of 1cm light path, measure OD values of all tubes at 412nm (adjust zero by distilled water)				

(2) Calculation:

Definition: Reacts at 37°C for 5 minutes, 1μmol/L GSH concentration decreasing (already deduct effect of nonenzymatic reaction) in reaction system per 0.1ml blood serum is considered as 1 enzyme activity unit (U).

Formula:

$$\text{Blood serum (or plasma) GSH-PX activity} = \frac{\text{OD}_{\text{Nonenzyme}} - \text{OD}_{\text{Enzyme}}}{\text{OD}_{\text{Standard}} - \text{OD}_{\text{Blank}}} \times \text{Standard solution concentration (20}\mu\text{mol/L)} \times \text{Dilution times (6*)} \times \text{Sample dilution times before assay}$$

Note: * According to operation table of enzymatic reaction, 0.4ml reaction solution is mixed with 2ml Reagent 2, this fact equals to 6 times dilution, so multiply with 6.

(4) Example of blood plasma optimal sampling concentration and optimal sampling volume probing:

① **Sample source:** Take whole blood from normal rat sockets, get blood plasma anticoagulated by heparin.

② **Sample pretreatment:**

Dilute blood plasma with physiological saline at ratio of 1:1, 1:4, 1:7, 1:14, 1:19 separately in order to make a series of blood plasma of different concentrations. Take 0.1ml a series of blood plasma of different concentrations to assay according to blood plasma (serum) assay operation table.

③ Results:

OD _{Blank}		0.041	
OD _{Standard}		0.163	
Sampling concentration	OD _{Enzyme}	OD _{Nonenzyme}	Inhibition ratio
1 : 1	0.117	0.519	77.46%
1 : 4	0.283	0.520	45.58%
1 : 7	0.365	0.518	29.53%
1 : 9	0.397	0.518	23.36%
1 : 14	0.421	0.516	18.41%
1 : 19	0.442	0.517	14.51%

④ Conclusion:

According to data above, optimal sampling concentration of 1:4 can make inhibition ratio (inhibition ratio= $((OD_{Contrast}-OD_{Sample})/OD_{Contrast}) \times 100\%$) in the range of 45%~55%. As result, it is better to take 0.1ml 1:4 diluted normal rat blood plasma for GSH-PX formal assay.

(5) Calculation example:

Take 0.1ml 1:4 diluted rat blood serum to assay. In results, OD_{Nonenzyme} is 0.475, OD_{Enzyme} is 0.293, OD_{Standard} is 0.165, OD_{Blank} is 0.041. Calculate as follows:

$$\text{Rat blood serum GSH-PX activity} = \frac{0.475-0.293}{0.165-0.041} \times 20 \times 6 \times 5 = 880.65 \text{ U}$$

7. ANNOUNCEMENTS

- (1) Hemolysate enzyme activity keeps stable at room temperature in 1 hour. So it is suggested to measure no longer than 1hour after sample dilution.
- (2) Blood samples must be fresh. Heparin anticoagulated blood can be stored at 4~8°C in fridge less than 48 hours.
- (3) Please make sure that erythrocytes are completely haemolyzed before measure blood GSH-PX activity (completely haemolyzed blood appears **transparent** towards light, **if it is not transparent enough, then you can freeze-thaw it once**. But erythrocytes of some rats and pigs can not be placed below 0°C or they will be hard to haemolyze. For example, erythrocytes of diabetic rats and some normal rats are very hard to haemolyze after freezing. It is better to take 1-2 samples to do pretesting before formal experiment.
- (4) Reagent 1 container should be washed completely, its working solution should be used soon after preparation.
- (5) 1mmol/L GSH, 0.1 mmol/L GSH, 20 μ mol/L GSH standard solutions should be used soon after preparation.
- (6) **Reaction time recording must be accurate** (for example, react in 37°C water bath for 5 minutes).
- (7) Taking and measuring of supernatant should be down in same day.
- (8) There are various methods to measure protein content in tissue, you can follow Experimental Methodology or buy our protein assay kits.

8. ABOUT COMPANY

<u>Nanjing Jiancheng Bioengineering Institute</u> <u>Nanjing Jiancheng Technology Co.Ltd.</u>			
Address:	Room 1106, Floor 11, New Li-Ji Mansion, No.258-27, Zhongyang Road, Nanjing	Telephone:	(025) 83360321 83360969 83113890
Postcode:	210009		83112287(finances) 83360272(technology)
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APPENDIX I: GSH STANDARD CURVE PREPARATION

1. Operation table:

Take 2ml 1mmol/L GSH standard solution, add 18ml GSH standard solvent to adjust volume to 20ml, 100 μ mol/L GSH standard working solution is prepared.

Tube No.	1	2	3	4	5	6
100 μ mol/L GSH standard (ml)	0	0.4	0.8	1.2	1.6	2
Reagent 2 (ml)	2	1.6	1.2	0.8	0.4	0
Reagent 3 (ml)	2	2	2	2	2	2
Reagent 4 (ml)	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5
Reagent 5 (ml)	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1
Mix sufficiently, place at room temperature for 15 minutes, transfer in cuvettes of 1cm light path, measure OD values of all tubes at 412nm (adjust zero by distilled water)						

2. Results:

Tube No.	1	2	3	4	5	6
Corresponding GSH standard concentration (μ mol/L)	0	20	40	60	80	100
Referenced OD	0.043	0.165	0.285	0.406	0.525	0.648
Absolute OD	0	0.122	0.242	0.363	0.482	0.605

3. Draw graph:

Use corresponding GSH standard concentration as x axis, use absolute OD values as y axis, draw standard curve:

